

RF Propagation and Interferences Challenges for UAVs Swarm Detection and Positioning

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Abstract—The usage of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) is considered a new technological trend able to solve some challenges of the modern society as dedicated transportation, on demand communication in special events, earth observation, smart agriculture and many others. But there are some challenges related to this fast development: air traffic monitoring, privacy assurance in some specified areas, protection of critical infrastructures, etc. All these challenges are supposing an accurate UAV detection and positioning. The present paper is contributing to a state-of-the-art investigation in this area focused on the UAVs swarm presence in a given environment and how UAVs nodes can be detected and localized. Also, we discuss the probable mechanisms that used for this purpose. Furthermore, we explain the challenges face the detection and positioning of UAVs in real world and propose some solutions to overcome these issues.

Keywords—unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV); detection; positioning; radio frequency (RF) spectrum; UAVs swarm; direction of arrival (DoA)

I. INTRODUCTION

The fast growing of the UAVs usage is posing a lot of challenges and threats regarding the access of such vehicles in several areas, such as protected perimeters, airports and also private properties. Moreover, many of them are small vehicles, difficult to detect and localize at a given distance. Such a challenge is amplified if there are more UAVs in the same area, flying independently or in a connected swarm. Moreover, in a global navigation satellite system (GNSS) denied environment, or where GNSS is unavailable or insufficient due to signal loss or interference, UAVs positioning becomes more difficult.

For the UAVs swarm detection, it is essential to know whether the communication node is aerial or not in a UAVs based network, hence, the network can select the operational protocol or regulation accordingly. Several schemes are used

for UAVs detection by estimating one of the following information: device elevation angle, device vertical location, delay spread, path loss and device velocity. After detecting the UAV device, the determination of its location, referring to zero coordinates is a vital process, since the accuracy of the UAV position, will facilitate the communication between network nodes directly. Moreover, with high frequency bands, where beamforming is adopted, positioning can play an important role in reducing the power consumption and latency time.

Several technologies can be used for UAVs positioning depending on the operating environment, i.e., indoor, urban, outdoor. For example, solutions such as observed time difference of arrival (O-TDoA) and uplink time difference of arrival (U-TDoA) are good candidates, even though they have low accuracy in vertical location estimation. Global navigation satellite system (GNSS) can provide accurate positioning information; however, it needs a complicated receiver, with a high power consumption, especially if there are too many UAVs in the network. Consequently, radio frequency (RF) based UAV detection and positioning techniques have attracted much interest recently. The main idea of these techniques is shown in Fig. 1, where reference nodes send messages to target UAV, which receives these signals and feedback them to the ground station that can localize the target UAV accordingly. In scenarios, where there is no ground station, e.g., flying ad hoc network (FANET) and UAVs swarms, UAVs nodes replace ground station and reference nodes, hence positioning of all nodes are determined according to selected reference nodes.

II. STATE OF THE ART

In the existing literature there are different detection and localization algorithms based on several frequency bands such as acoustic, optical, radar or radio frequency (RF) spectrum monitoring, but most of them are taking into consideration only the presence of individual drones.

Fig .1. RF based UAV detection and positioning.

A. Single UAV detection and positioning

In [1] the authors propose a novel method for positioning and monitoring individual drones, in which the FHSS signal received by a universal software radio peripheral (USRP) platform is processed and trilateration technique is applied to establish the position of the drone. In [2] the authors present a comprehensive review on the attacks that have been performed via UAVs in different regions of the globe, the main principles of communication used, the monitoring techniques and the neutralization ones. The authors of [3] show that the navigation systems are affected by the existence of UAVs, that produce perturbations of the radio channel, and propose to solve that issue using automated monitoring and control of the satellite links state. In [4] a comprehensive review of the spectrum management for UAV applications is performed and several spectrum management solutions that use blockchain are identified. In [5] a multi-dimensional signal positioning system is proposed, that, at first, evaluates the state of the communication channel (CSI) between the UAV and the controller and, based on that, it identifies the RF fingerprint of the UAV, where a 1.2m median 3D positioning accuracy is obtained. The authors of [7] propose an enhanced, low-cost RFID identification system that determines the position of an UAV in indoor environment with enhanced precision and ensure its autonomous navigation, while the authors of [8] propose a positioning technique based on aerial-anchors that proved to offer satisfactory results even in shadowed areas.

The authors in [9] merge between GNSS, visual, depth and inertial data to localize UAVs in real-time. Moreover, this scheme can work without GNSS in urban and indoor environments and provide an 8 cm as a localization accuracy on average. In [10], a 3D space based algorithm has been proposed to detect, identify and recognize UAVs that intrude in restricted airspace. In this work, a real data set, collected during field tests, is used to develop the detection scheme, which depends on clustering and conditional complementary filtration. The authors in [11] proposed a camera based UAV detection algorithm in 3D space, where it estimates both the location and altitude of UAV without environmental awareness. This work provides a simple and accurate UAV detection algorithm which is suitable to any scenario. In [12], the authors proposed a ground-based monocular positioning

system for UAV in real use cases scenarios, using a light emitting diode, attached to the UAV. In contrast to other schemes proposed in the literature, this one only needs a very simple infrastructure and calibration to be deployed in GNSS-denied environment. This technique uses conventional neural network whilst considering uncertainty propagation to achieve nearly 41 cm RMSE of UAV localization. The authors in [13] proposed a self-localization based UAV detection technique. This approach implements the extended Kalman filter algorithm in the data collected by the onboard electric motor, accelerometers, gyroscopes, and altimeter to estimate drone position respected to a ground platform. In [14], based on acoustic information obtained from a microphone array system, the authors proposed a drone detection approach to be used in GNSS denied scenarios. This scheme mainly depends on the idea that the drone's rotors make noise when they revolve at high speed. The accuracy of this approach is nearly similar to the one obtained using global positioning system.

B. UAVs swarm detection and positioning

The presence of two or more such UAVs will increase the difficulty of accurate detection and identification of such vehicles, especially in a noisy environment or in the presence of different interferences or other countermeasures, especially if the goal is to detect, identify and track the position of different UAVs, not only simultaneously, but also in real time. The authors of [15] consider the threats given by the UAVs swarms for several national security spaces and for critical infrastructures, presenting also some algorithms based on the coherent long-time integration (LTI) technique and gridless sparse technique to detect and localize UAVs in a swarm and, based on their simulations results, considers that such methods as good candidates in terms of UAV detection and localization accuracy. [16] analyses the threats given by the presence of obstacles in the navigation of the elements that constitute the swarm and how the collisions may be avoided, but such methods, based on trajectory prediction, may contribute to the UAVs localization and tracking inside a swarm. In [17] a multi-target detection and tracking algorithm for UAV swarms is presented; but the same concept can be also implemented inversely, i.e., to detect and track the swarm elements individually. The authors of [18] investigate the motion-based detection methods of the UAVs swarm elements and develop in MATLAB a simulation platform to assess its performances. In [19], the authors proposed a digital coding based technique to eliminate the noise effect and establish an empty window to detect objects, where various target properties, e.g., auto-correlation, cross-correlation, and ambiguity function, are used to optimize and improve detection of static and dynamic elements of a multi-target environment with doppler existence. The authors in [20] discuss unmanned vehicles positioning in specific use cases in ports, e.g., containers yard and shore space, where they proposed using cartographer simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) algorithm to localize nodes depending on reflections received from targets. Also, they considered the effect of speed and vibration on positioning information.

Mainly, the accuracy, complexity and required time of the positioning process depends on the mechanism used in determining the UAVs location. The received signal strength

based schemes are very simple and straightforward to be implemented [21], but they are easily affected by signal attenuations, multipath effects, and blockage. Thus, these mechanisms are unsuitable to UAVs swarm networks, especially in highly dynamic and severe environment. Angle of arrival (AoA), also called direction of arrival (DoA), is a large category of positioning techniques that are used in UAVs positioning. These techniques can provide the 6 degrees of freedom of the target UAV node, i.e., the three x, y, and z coordinates, and the orientation angles, pitch, roll, and yaw. Hence, AoA based positioning mechanisms are widely used for UAVs swarms due to their applicability and efficiency. In association with other techniques, especially with the ones using Doppler radars, it helps in accurate detection of the target position, including the case of multiple targets. In [22] a such DoA algorithm using micro-UAVs swarm is investigated. Few fast DoA algorithm based on reweighted atomic-norm minimization (RAM) dedicated to UAVs swarm positioning is analyzed in [23]. A new trend in DoA estimation, able to decrease the imprecision due of the UAVs movement is the one that uses reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS) as it is presented, for example, in [24]. Moreover, time of arrival-based localization schemes can be an interesting direction of research, however they need clock synchronization between all UAV nodes, which is highly difficult and complicated. Although two-ray ranging algorithm can overcome this issue, as presented in [25]-[27], a degradation in performance can easily occur due to clock drift, which is a result of unpredictable response delay and inefficient oscillators in UAVs sensors. Furthermore, a higher node number leads to an increase in cost, latency and energy consumption. In [28]-[31], time difference of arrival (TDoA) based mechanisms have been proposed to reduce the aforementioned challenges. However, TDoA needs time synchronization between network nodes, and the technique is reliable to non-line of sight paths and noise effects. In general, time-based mechanisms suffer different problems which make them unapplicable to UAV swarm detection and positioning.

There are also other detection algorithms based on RF spectrum monitoring, but most of them are considering the presence of individual drones. The presence of two or more UAVs will increase the difficulty of accurate detection and identification of such vehicles in real time, especially in a noisy environment or in the presence of different interferences or other countermeasures.

III. CHALLENGES AND OPEN DIRECTIONS

RF based positioning techniques have some limitations due to the nature of the signal in this band. First, the channel conditions between the UAVs and the reference nodes, e.g., propagation, penetration, and interference characteristics, has a high impact on the localization accuracy, cost and power consumption needed. For example, beyond 6 GHz bands are susceptible to high propagation losses due to distances between transmitter and receiver. Also, signals from these frequency domain cannot penetrate static obstacles, which causes higher need for multiple reference nodes to efficiently cover the environment and accurately detect and localize UAVs nodes. Moreover, high interference degrades the signal power, hence

positioning information can be lost or delayed. Additionally, it is very difficult to obtain UAV orientation using RF based positioning schemes, except by using AoA based mechanisms. Furthermore, in blockage reliable bands, e.g., millimeter wave and terahertz, positioning information can be unavailable due to signal blocking by static and dynamic obstacles. Besides, with higher bands, the coverage of the nodes shrinks, hence more reference nodes are needed for positioning, thus increasing implementation cost. In addition, energy consumption is a vital factor in UAVs swarm network, because if a certain node dies due to high operations or other reasons, this will affect the overall network performance. Hence, this metric should be considered when proposing RF based UAVs detection and positioning. These issues do not only impact the positioning accuracy and the performance of the network, but also can lead to lose of control on UAVs nodes.

Several solutions can be adopted to overcome these issues; first, combine RF with sensors-based techniques to improve positioning accuracy, provide orientation information, minimize noise effect on measured values, and reduce implementation cost. However, this solution can come with a limitation if one technology faces a problem, e.g., RF signal can be blocked, camera can lose visibility, and some sensors can be affected by magnetic fields. In addition, proposing cooperation between several RF bands at the same time to localize nodes, as it has been discussed for another application in [32], can be a promising direction, but it will increase the cost and the complexity of the UAVs swarm network. Moreover, artificial intelligent (AI) based techniques can be good candidates in this field due their efficiency. However, large, real, and trusted datasets shall be collected and evaluated. Also, providing real-time positioning information using machine learning based techniques will be under question. Furthermore, deploying reflecting intelligent surfaces (RISs) in UAVs swarm network can help in accurately detecting and positioning nodes.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The presence of an important number of UAVs in a given area, both if they are structured and connected swarms or only a number of independent aerial vehicles conducts to a lot of additional difficulties in the accurate detection and positioning of such vehicles. The engineering world is aware on these difficulties and the present paper is trying to add a contribution in investigating several of the latest results highlighted in the scientific literature regarding the detection and positioning of UAVs swarm used RF based techniques especially in GNSS denied environments. This work discussed several existing schemes proposed to detect and localize the UAVs. Moreover, we explain the main mechanisms that are used in this process. Furthermore, we discussed the challenges that appeared in RF based UAVs positioning techniques and tries to suggest some directions to overcome them.

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